

Antibacterial Studies of 7-(α -Substituted sulphonamido)Methyl- and 7-(α -Substituted sulphonamido)Phenyl-8-Hydroxyquinolines†

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SULPHONAMIDES are drugs of established therapeutic importance. When they react with 8-hydroxyquinoline in presence of formaldehyde, Mannich type reaction takes place and 7-substituted-8-hydroxyquinolines¹ are obtained. It was decided, therefore, to synthesize compounds of structure (I) derived from the above reaction.

R = 2-pyrimidinyl, 2,6-dimethoxy-4-pyrimidinyl, 4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidinyl, 2,6-dimethyl-4-pyrimidinyl; R' = methyl or phenyl.

Experimental

Preparation of 7-substituted methyl-8-hydroxyquinolines: Formaldehyde (0.005 mole), sulphonamide (0.005 mole) and 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.005 mole) were dissolved in methanol (50 ml). The pH was adjusted to 3, the mixture heated on water bath for 4 hr and left at room temp. The product was filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallized from acetone. Nitrogen was estimated by a modified Kjeldahl method² and sulphur by Messenger's method. Results of elemental analysis are depicted in Table 1.

The infra red spectra recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer model-237 showed sharp and strong bands at 760 cm^{-1} (NH deformation)³,

characteristic bands of the benzene ring near 1590 cm^{-1} , pyrimidine ring near 1560 cm^{-1} and 3240 cm^{-1} , phenolic C-O stretching near 1275 cm^{-1} ⁴, $-\text{SO}_2$ stretching near 1040 cm^{-1} ⁵ and bands near 3580 and 1190 cm^{-1} due to $-\text{OH}$ deformation mode⁶.

Antibacterial studies :

10 mg compounds A to H (Table 1) were separately dissolved in 10 ml of aqueous alcohol (50% v/v). Filter paper disc diffusion plate method, as described earlier^{7,8}, was adopted for antibacterial studies. Paper discs of 5 mm diameter (Whatman filter paper No. 1) were soaked in solution of the respective samples, drained and placed on the spore seeded plates made of nutrient agar (OXCID) as medium (5 mm height). A control test was simultaneously run by placing a blank disc at the centre of the same petri dish. The dishes were incubated at $37.5 \pm 1^\circ$ and the inhibitory effect was noted against the test organism after 24 hr by measuring the developed zones of inhibition. The recorded zones of inhibition were compared with those caused by the standard sulphanilamide under identical conditions.

In vitro efficacy of compounds A to H against *Escherichia coli*, *Vibrio cholerae*, *Achromobacter hydrophilis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Plesiomonas schigellaides*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Citrobacter* and *C. ovis* being studied and the results are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that compounds A, B and D are more effective against *Escherichia coli*, while compounds, A, E, G and H show half the potency as compared to the parent drug against *V. cholerae*, *A. hydrophilis* and *P. mirabilis*. Compound A is more potent and E, G and H are more or less equally potent as compared to the standard sulphanilamide against *K. pneumoniae*. Compounds A, G and H also reveal similar effect against *S. typhi*. Decreased potency of most of the compounds as compared to the standard one is also observed against *P. schi-*

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R	R'	Mol. formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
				N	S
A	2-Pyrimidinyl	-CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	16.66 (16.62)	7.66 (7.60)
B	2,6-Dimethoxy-4-pyrimidinyl	-OH	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	14.46 (14.55)	6.71 (6.65)
C	4,6-Dimethyl-2-pyrimidinyl	-CH ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	15.66 (15.59)	7.19 (7.12)
D	2,6-Dimethyl-4-pyrimidinyl	-OH	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	15.66 (15.59)	7.19 (7.12)
E	2-Pyrimidinyl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	14.56 (14.49)	6.64 (6.72)
F	2,6-Dimethoxy-4-pyrimidinyl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	12.94 (12.89)	5.82 (5.89)
G	4,6-Dimethyl-2-pyrimidinyl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.82 (13.70)	6.30 (6.26)
H	2,6-Dimethyl-4-pyrimidinyl	-C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.85 (13.70)	6.30 (6.26)

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TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF 7-(α -SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDO)METHYL AND 7-(α -SUBSTITUTED SULPHONAMIDO)PHENYL-8-HYDROXYQUINOLINES

Organism	Zone of inhibition (mm) by								
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	S'
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	20	18	08	13	07	10	06	12	—
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	21	—	—	08	18	10	18	18	35
<i>Achromobacter hydrophilis</i>	—	18	12	—	—	16	17	06	35
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	—	08	—	13	12	14	12	09	24
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	23	10	10	—	18	10	19	20	21
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	22	—	16	14	—	—	20	24	22
<i>Plesiomonas shigellaides</i>	20	28	14	10	20	18	26	08	41
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	23	06	08	—	—	12	20	10	—
<i>Citrobacter</i>	14	20	10	12	16	10	28	18	36
<i>C. ovis</i>	30	24	12	—	15	09	10	—	40

S' = Sulphanilamide.

gellaiides, *Citrobacter* and *C. ovis*. Compounds A and G show a promising potency over the standard compound against *P. vulgaris*. Thus, the *in vitro* screening of the synthesized compounds against the organisms, although indicative of decreased potency, cannot be ruled out for quantitative screening. This decreased activity may be due to the lack of absorption under prevalent conditions.

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A Quick Method of Two Dimensional Thin Layer Chromatographic Separation of Human Serum Phospholipids and Their Identification

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ALL the 9-10 human serum phospholipids have been specifically extracted from 1 ml normal human serum by a particular organic solvent and resolved

and developed in two dimensional thin layer chromatogram. A specific solvent pair which gives straight solvent front (both ways), runs quickly, evaporates readily and possesses other favourable properties, has been used. Using the serum extract of normal healthy person, each of the nine phospholipids has been identified against known compounds and a 'standard map' of human serum phospholipids has been prepared. Total time required to study a pathological serum is only 4 hr.

Experimental

Selection of solvent pair :

The first requirement was the selection of a suitable solvent pair for two dimensional, thin layer chromatography. Considerable work has been done for the separation of phospholipids and getting all the 9-10 human serum phospholipids resolved and developed in the chromatogram. Nevertheless, many workers in the past have been confronted with the problem of selecting a suitable solvent pair for this purpose. Because of the polar nature of the compounds, a more polar solvent is required to move and develop them on silica gel layers. One of the widely used solvent mixtures that has been accepted by majority of workers is chloroform-methanol-water mixture of different proportions, such as (65 : 25 : 4)¹, (60 : 35 : 8)², etc. A number of solvent pairs have been tried but complete resolution and development of all the 9-10 phospholipids could not be achieved. It has been found in this laboratory after a long study, that if the universally accepted solvent system, chloroform-methanol-water is utilized in different proportions and the plate is coated with neutral silica gel the nine phospholipids could easily be resolved and developed. The first solvent used was chloroform-methanol-water mixture of 60 : 35 : 8 ratio and the second was a mixture of the same components in 65 : 25 : 4 ratio. Merits and demerits of this solvent pair have been discussed later.

Preparation of the plate :

20 × 20 cm glass plates were coated with silica gel G (Type 60, Art 7731, E. Merck) and used. For five plates, 40 g of the silica gel was taken in a glass

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